

**Synthesis and Pharmacological Screening of
some New 1-Phenyl-3-(4-substituted-
phenoxyphenyl)-5-(substituted-benzy-
lidino)thiobarbituric Acids**

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BARBITURIC acid derivatives and barbital possess various pharmacological activities¹. Several pyrimidines also possess promising hypotensive activity². These observations prompted us to synthesise some new barbiturates.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian A60D instrument using TMS as internal reference. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G plates using benzene-methanol (9 : 1) as solvent.

4-Nitrodiphenyl ethers (1a, b) and 4-aminodiphenyl ethers (2a, b) were prepared by the reported method³.

1-Phenyl-3-(4-substituted-phenoxyphenyl) thiourea (4a, b): A mixture of 4-aminodiphenyl ethers (0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (5; 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (30 ml) was refluxed for 2 h and then the solvent was evaporated. The resulting solid was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and recrystallised from ethanol: 4a (R=H; 88%), m.p. 152°; 4b (R=RH₃; 85%), m.p. 145°.

1-Phenyl-3-(4-substituted-phenoxyphenyl)thiobarbituric acid (5a, b): To 4a, b (0.015 mol) were added malonic acid (0.02 mol) and acetyl chloride (7 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h and then poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°): 5a (R=H; 70%), m.p. 110°; 5b (R=CH₃; 77%), m.p. 98°; δ (CDCl₃+DMSO) 6.2–7.1 (14H, m, ArH) and 1.4–1.8 (2H, s, CH₂); for both compounds ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 920–2 940 (CH), 1 200 (C=S) and 1 700 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

1-Phenyl-3-(4-substituted-phenoxyphenyl)-5-(substituted-benzylidino)thiobarbituric acid (6a–p): A mixture of the appropriate 5 (0.01 mol), appropriate aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.015 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (Table 1): for all compounds ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 920–2 940 (CH) and 1 200 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (CDCl₃+DMSO) 6.68–7.42 (15H, m, 18 × ArH and C=CH).

Toxicity and gross CNS effects: All the compounds (except 6m) were screened for acute toxicity and gross CNS activities. Graded doses of compounds were administered intraperitoneally to albino mice (18–22 g) of either sex and observed over a period of 24 h. Approximate LD_{50} was calculated according to the reported method⁴. For observing gross behavioural action the effect of 1/5th of LD_{50} dose was observed on the spontaneous motor activity (SMA) and reactivities to sound and touch.

Compounds 6k, l, n were found toxic in nature as is evident from their low LD_{50} value (681 mg/kg). Structure-activity relationship reveals that when $\text{R}=\text{CH}_3$ the compounds possess toxicity whereas similar compounds having $\text{R}=\text{H}$ were non-toxic in nature. Except compound 6l, all were found to be CNS stimulants as they increased the SMA and reactivities to sound and touch.

Cardiovascular activity: Compounds 6a–i and

6l were screened for cardiovascular activity in cats (3–4 kg) of either sex, anaesthetised with sodium pentobarbital (35 mg/kg ip) at doses of 1.0 and 5.0 mg/kg. The right common carotid artery was cannulated and the pressure was recorded on a Kymograph. Respiration was recorded through a Marey's tambour after cannulating the trachea on the Kymograph. All the test substances and reference standards acetyl choline (0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), adrenaline hydrochloride (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), histamine acid phosphate (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) were administered through an indwelling polythene cannula in the right femoral vein.

The compounds showed in significant activity as they produced only a transient hypotensive effect.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 6a–p*

Compd. no.	R'	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
R = H			
6a	4-Nitro	100	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{S}$
b	4-Hydroxy	140	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$
c	4-Chloro	110	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{SCl}$
d	4-Carboxy	105	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}$
e	4-Dimethylamino	138	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{S}$
f	4-Benzoyloxy	128	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$
g	4-Amino	117	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S}$
h	3-Hydroxy-4-methoxy	120	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}$
R = CH_3			
i	4-Nitro	102	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6\text{S}$
j	4-Hydroxy	180	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$
k	4-Chloro	202	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{SCl}$
l	4-Carboxy	160	$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}$
m	4-Dimethylamino	130	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{37}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S}$
n	4-Benzoyloxy	160	$\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$
o	4-Amino	124	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S}$
p	3-Hydroxy-4-methoxy	210	$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}$

*All the compounds gave satisfactory analyses for C, H, N and S; Yield = 60–70%.

Anti-inflammatory activity: Compounds 6a–i were tested for anti-inflammatory activity using reported method⁵. The experiment was carried out on albino rats (100–120 g) of either sex were divided into groups of five animals. The difference in consecutive measurements (oedema) of the rats in control group and drug-tested group was compared. Phenyl butazone (30 mg/kg) was used as the standard and the activity was calculated in percentage.

Compounds 6f–h showed inhibition against carrageenin induced oedema ranging from 24–29% in rats at the dose of 1/10th of their LD_{50} values. Structure-activity relationship reveals that when $\text{R}=\text{H}$, the compounds exhibited anti-inflammatory activity and the corresponding compounds having $\text{R}=\text{CH}_3$, showed no activity.

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References

- J. HONO, M. SYPMIEWSKA and W. E. CHOJNACK, *Pol. J. Pharmacol. Pharmacy*, 1978, 30, 55; F. F. BLICK and R. H. COX, *Med. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 1; E. FISCHER and A. DILTHEY, *Justus Liebig's Ann. Chem.*, 1904, 375, 334.

2. W. CRANSTON, in "Antihypertensive Therapy", ed. F. GROSS, Springer, Berlin, 1966, p. 184; H. L. YALE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 85, 123965; G. L. MORRISON, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 85, 192759.
3. Beilsteins Handbuch Der Organischen chemie vierte Auflage. ; 6, 394.
4. C. S. WEIL, *Biometrics*, 1952, 8, 249.
5. C. A. WINTER, E. A. RISLEY and G. W. NUSS, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1962, 111, 544.